

Intelligent monitoring of joint friction for industrial robots

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Abstract—The development of a model for the prediction of the friction in robotic joints by taking into account the working condition is a crucial task for many applications including: predictive maintenance, identification of impact without force sensors, human-robot interaction without force sensors, implementation of virtual force sensors, and others. However, such a model is not easy to develop because friction depend on many factors including velocity and temperature. On the basis of theoretical and experimental studies on different industrial manipulators, this paper explores this field showing the main factors influencing the friction and giving a solid base for the development of suitable predictive models.

Keywords—Industrial Robots, Friction, Temperature

I. INTRODUCTION

In different intelligent machines advanced models are investigated to obtain information on the internal status of the axis without using specific sensors. Application examples include the prediction of friction for predictive maintenance, identification of impact [1], [2], [3], [4] and human-robot interaction without force sensors [5], implementation of virtual force sensors [4], and others.

Friction have been represented in different ways ranging from elementary models (e.g. Coulomb or viscous model) to more sophisticated models, see, for example, [6], [7]. Friction depends on many factors including the nature of the sliding surfaces, the compressing force, the relative velocity between the surfaces and the properties of the lubricant. Many of these factors depend on the temperature, and the temperature changes during the robot working period due to the heat generated by the friction itself [8], [11].

In robotics applications it is often assumed that the torque τ_i of the i -th motor is the sum of terms related to the robot dynamics and a term that depends on friction, that is:

$$\tau_i = \tau(Q, \dot{Q}, \ddot{Q}) + \tau_{fi} + J^t F_e \quad (1)$$

where Q is the joint coordinate vector, the dots mark the time derivative, J is the jacobian and F_e are the external forces. The dependence of friction from the velocity is generally expressed in polynomial form by using the sign function ($\text{sign}(x)=x/|x|$ for $x \neq 0$, and $\text{sign}(x)=0$ for $x=0$):

$$\tau_{fi} = a_i \text{sign}(\dot{q}_i) + b_i \dot{q}_i + c_i \text{sign}(\dot{q}_i) \dot{q}_i^2 + d_i \dot{q}_i^3 \quad (2)$$

Experience shows that the coefficients a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i depends on the temperature [9]. While generally friction decreases with temperature (fig. 1a), it may happen for some gear model that at low velocity it increases with it (fig. 1b). A possible reason is that the viscosity of lubricant decreases with temperature and at high temperature and low speed the viscosity is not sufficient to create separation between the sliding surfaces [10].

Fig. 1. Example of friction torque in function of the joint velocity and the increasing joint temperature T .

II. ADVANCED MODEL

Practical experimentations have shown that, in some industrial robots, the coefficients of eq. (2) can be assumed as linearly dependent with temperature:

$$a_i = a_{i0} + k_i(T - T_0)$$

with $k_i < 0$ and a simple first order thermal model of the joint is sufficient to represent and predict the joint temperature and the consequent friction torque ([8], [12]). However further experiments have shown that for some robots a second order model is necessary (Fig. 2). Two temperatures T_i are considered: that of the gear, and that of the surroundings area. Two masses and thermal capacity C_i are assigned to this part, and suitable transmission constants K_i are assumed:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dT_1}{dt} = \frac{(pT_1+q)-K_1(T_1-T_2)}{C_1} \\ \frac{dT_2}{dt} = \frac{K_1(T_1-T_2)-K_2(T_2-T_e)}{C_2} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

with $W_{in} = \tau_f \dot{\vartheta}$, $p = \tau_{fe} \dot{\vartheta} \alpha$, and $q = \tau_{fe} \dot{\vartheta} (\beta - \alpha T)$

Fig. 2. Joint thermal model with two thermal capacities and two temperatures.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Experiments were performed on an anthropomorphic industrial manipulator Efort Model ER3A-C60, 23kg weight, 3kg payload. Heating and cooling experiments have been performed by alternating working cycles (high speed alternating motion) with test trajectories (fig. 3) with constant velocities intervals. Friction torque has been obtained by subtracting the dynamic and gravity effects (eq. (1)) from the measured motor torque.

Fig. 3. Example of friction torque and joint velocity at different joint temperature T (test trajectory).

The tests were repeated with different duty cycles (fig. 4a) obtaining different transient responses (fig. 4b) and collecting sufficient data to estimate all the constant of the model.

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Fig. 4. Different duty cycles (33%, 50%, 67%, 100%) and friction torque at 60% of the maximum velocity versus time for joint 4.

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